

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

STUDY OF ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON THE COMPOSITE- TO-METAL DOUBLE LAP SHEAR JOINTS

Reporter: Qian Zhang
Time: 08/12 (2019)

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Contents

1、 Background

2、 Environmental effects on the adhesive

3、 Environmental effects on the interface

4、 Environmental effects on the tensile

behavior of double lap joint

5、 Conclusion

1、Background

- Embedded resistance wire for deicing in the rotor
- Counterweights

Trend of composite material Used in aircraft field

B787fuselage

schematic view of the rotor

Lightning damage of composite

Service environment

2 Experimental effects on the adhesive

2.1 Experiments

➤ Test of adhesive

Adhesive specimen

test set-up

Moisture absorption specimen

room temperature/dry (RD)
Room temperature/wet (RW)
Elevated temperature/dry (ED)
elevated temperature/wet (EW)

All of specimens were performed using Instron 8801 electro-hydraulic servo fatigue test machine (precision 0.1%) with matching conditioning chamber

2 Experimental effects on the adhesive

2.1 Experiments

➤ Tensile test results of adhesive

elastic modulus

tensile strength

Elongations of adhesive test

$$T_{gw} = T_{g0} - gM \quad T^* = \frac{T_{gw} - T}{T_{g0} - T_0} \quad E = E^0 (T^*)^a \quad S = S^0 (T^*)^c$$

It can be seen the moisture has a minimal effect on the elongation of the adhesive, and the elongation of adhesive increase linearly with the increase of temperature.

3 Environmental effects on the interface

3.1 Experiments

➤ Specimens and Test procedures

DCB specimen for RD, RW, and ED

DCB specimen for EW

RD and RW

EW

Test set-ups for DCB specimens

Test set-ups for ENF specimens

3 Environmental effects on the interface

3.2 Results

➤ fracture energy release rate

RD

RW

ED

EW

Load-displacement curves of composite/adhesive DCB specimens

DCB specimens

ENF specimens

Damage morphologies composite/adhesive specimens Load-displacement curves of ENF

3 Environmental effects on the interface

3.2 Results

Damage morphologies
metal/adhesive specimens

Fracture toughness of composite/adhesive interface

environ ments	G_{IC} (J/m ²)	G_{IIC} (J/m ²)
RD	620	5140
ED	440	2880
RW	438	450
EW	315	245

Fracture toughness of metal/adhesive interface

2304	7510
1765	5100
1510	5300
2093	2450

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.1 Experiments

➤ Manufacture and test of the joint

制备工艺

Geometry and dimensions

Composite : T800/AC531

Metal: Al-7075-T6, anodized with phosphoric acid

Adhesive : SY-14M-III epoxy resin

Test set-up

The specimens were divided into four groups: RD, RW, ED and EW.

The static tensile tests of bulk adhesive were performed using Instron 8801 electro-hydraulic servo fatigue test machine.

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.2 Numerical investigation

➤ Mechanical model

FE model and the details of DLSJ

the 8-node reduced integration solid elements (C3D8R) were used in Abaqus/Standard

0-thickness cohesive elements were introduced to simulate the interfaces in the joint.

Each composite ply and the adhesive layer were set as a single element though their thicknesses, and more fine meshes were used in the bonded area of the specimen.

A half of the model was established here.

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.2 Numerical investigation

➤ Hygrothermal mechanical properties

	composite			
	RD	RW	ED	EW
E_{11} (GPa)	173	173	171	169
E_{22}, E_{33} (GPa)	8.47	7.8	6.2	5.5
G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	4.25	4.17	3.71	3.47
G_{23} (GPa)	3.6	3.5	3.15	2.98
$\nu_{23}, \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}$	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34
X_T (MPa)	3020	3007	2969	2950
X_C (MPa)	1342	1315	1232	1193
Y_T (MPa)	62.9	59.2	48.8	44.2
Y_C (MPa)	211	199	163	148
S_{12}, S_{13} (MPa)	142	132	105	94
S_{23} (MPa)	101	94	75	67

adhesive

	E (GPa)	ν	S_{mises} (MPa)	E_p
RD	3.73	0.35	66	0.003
RW	3.33	0.33	59.8	0.003
ED	1.14	0.40	38	0.083
EW	1.01	0.33	20.3	0.083

expansion coefficient

	(/°C)	(/°C)	(/°C)
composite	1.00E-07	2.60E-05	2.60E-05
adhesive	4E-5	4E-5	4E-5
Al-7075	2.35E-5	2.35E-5	2.35E-5

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.2 Numerical investigation

➤ Hygrothermal stress

For the RW group, the maximum stress appear at the inner of adhesive.

For the ED group, the maximum stress appear around the adhesive.

For the EW group, the initial damage occurs around the adhesive.

Hygrothermal status

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.2 Numerical investigation

➤ Result

the nominal shear strength (ultimate load divided by bonding area) is introduced here to verify the validity of FEM

$$\tau = \frac{F_{ult}}{2bl}$$

Failure modes

nominal shear strength

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.3 Discussion

➤ The effect of adhesive thickness

For RD groups, compared with the original model, the ultimate load were improved by -6.5%, -0.7%, 15.7% and 18.9%.

For RW groups, the ultimate load were improved by -7.1%, 1.9%、 7.2% and 7.6%.

For RW groups, the ultimate load were improved by - 20.1%, 27.5%, 32.6% and 32.2%.

For RW groups, the ultimate load were improved by - 17.0%, 18.0%, 84.0% and 30.1%.

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.3 Discussion

- The effect of preparation technics

The preparation technics (as shown in left) were adopted.

preparation technics

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.3 Discussion

➤ results

4 Environmental effects on the tensile behavior of double lap joint

4.3 Discussion

The ultimate load

The ultimate load of Mode II under ED environment is much larger than other two.

Deformation diagram in ED

The innerstress of adhesive in ED environment

4.3 Discussion

➤ results

5 Conclusion

- The moisture and thermal environments have significant effect on elastic modulus and tensile strength of adhesive, and also have significant effect on the interfacial properties.
- The moisture has a minimal effect on the elongation of the adhesive, and the elongation of adhesive increase linearly with the increase of the temperature.
- The failure modes of DLSJs corresponding to the dry and wet environments were different. The main damage was adhesive failure in dry group, while the main damage was interlaminar failure in wet group.

Thanks for your attention!